

Potential drug-drug interactions and their associated factors at the University Children's Hospital in Syria: A cross-sectional study

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Abstract

Objective: Polypharmacy among pediatric inpatients is common and exposes children to the risk of drug-drug interactions (DDIs). This study aimed to characterize potential DDIs (pDDIs) and their associated risk factors among pediatric inpatients.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted over six months at the University Children's Hospital in Damascus. A total of 575 children taking two drugs or more participated. pDDIs were checked using Lexi-Interact® software. pDDIs within risk category B (No action needed), C (Monitor therapy), D (Modify regimen), and X (Avoid combination) were included. Logistic regression was used to identify factors associated with pDDIs.

Results: At least one pDDI was detected in 49.7% of children. Overall, 744 pDDIs were identified. The majority of pDDIs were within risk category C (71.6%), followed by D (14%), B (12.8%), and X (1.6%). The most common pDDIs were: aminoglycosides - penicillins (n=56), aminoglycosides - cephalosporins (n=27), and vitamin D analogs - calcium salts (n=23). The number of prescribed drugs and nervous system drugs were significantly associated with the presence of pDDIs.

Conclusion: pDDIs among pediatric inpatients were prevalent. The majority of the pDDIs were within risk category C, which necessitates therapy monitoring and necessary action to avoid adverse consequences.